

Estimated source population sizes for WHO STEPS surveys with publicly available data

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Abstract

The World Health Organization provides researchers with free access to microdata from surveys conducted as part of its STEPwise approach to NCD risk factor surveillance program (WHO STEPS). When pooling data from multiple surveys, researchers must account for the size of the source population of each survey. Currently, there are no ready-to-use estimates of the source populations for the surveys. In this report, we describe the calculation and validation of source population size estimates and provide a dataset of population sizes to be used by researchers working with WHO STEPS data.

Introduction

The World Health Organization organizes the collection of data on the prevalence of non-communicable diseases and their risk factors in low- and middle-income countries through its STEPwise approach to NCD risk factor surveillance program,¹ and provides researchers with free access to the data from many of the surveys through its microdata repository website.²

Any researcher wanting to combine data from two or more surveys in a single analysis must account for the relative sizes of the survey source populations, since these can be vastly different. At present, there is no

ready-to-use resource that lists estimates of the source population sizes for all the WHO STEPS surveys. This report describes the creation and validation of such a dataset and includes a table of source population sizes for public health researchers to use when analyzing WHO STEPS data. While total population estimates by year and country are readily available online, the dataset described in this report explicitly accounts for the following three important properties of the WHO STEPS surveys:

- Different surveys used different age ranges for eligibility (and the source population estimate should only include people in the eligible age range for each survey).
- Data collection for some surveys spanned more than one calendar year (meaning that one must take a weighted average of the source population estimate for each of the years that data was collected for a specific survey)
- Some surveys were not designed to be nationally representative (rather, representing a smaller geographical area), and the source population estimate should only reflect the size of the population in the represented area.

Methods

Underlying assumptions

A priori, we assumed that the eligible population in a survey area in calendar year i could be calculated according to Equation 1, where it is termed a_i . The estimated size of the total population of the survey country (according to the United Nations) is termed b_i , while c_i is the estimated proportion of the survey country population that is within the eligible age range for the survey (according to the United Nations). Both b_i and c_i are easily derived from tabular datasets available online.³ To account for surveys that were only subnationally representative, we include the factor $\frac{d_i}{e_i}$. d_i and e_i are both calculated from geospatial analysis of datasets that list the population count in a global grid with cell size approximately 1×1 km, overlaid with geometric datasets defining the size and shape of administrative units. d_i is the size of the population in the survey area (all ages combined), and e_i is the size of the population in the whole country (all ages combined). Since the geospatial datasets used in the analyses presented in this report did not contain information on age structure, an important assumption behind Equation 1 is that the population structure (in terms of age and sex) is the same everywhere in the country.

Equation 1

$$a_i = b_i \times c_i \times \frac{d_i}{e_i}$$

Some readers might wonder why we chose to combine population estimates from multiple sources (tabular data stratified by sex and age from the United Nations, and geospatial data on total population), when the

WorldPop program provides geospatial datasets of population size estimates stratified by age and sex.⁴ However, these datasets are only available for the years 2015-2030, and most of the WHO STEPS datasets that were designed to be subnationally representative took place before 2015.

As described above, data collection for some surveys spanned multiple calendar years. Hence, the final estimate of the source population size (a_{tot}) was calculated according to Equation 2. For each calendar year, f_i is the fraction of the time spent on data collection that was spent in the i^{th} year (so that $\sum_i f_i = 1$).

Equation 2

$$a_{tot} = \sum_i a_i \times f_i = \sum_i b_i \times c_i \times \frac{d_i}{e_i} \times f_i$$

Data sources

Estimates of population (both total, and stratified by sex and one-year age groups) for all years between 2000 and 2024 were downloaded from the website of the Population Division of the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations.⁴ In the remainder of this report, these data will be referred to as "UN" population estimates.

Geospatial population data were downloaded from LandScan Global⁵ (hereafter referred to as "LandScan"), WorldPop Global⁶ (hereafter referred to as "WorldPop") and GlobPOP⁷ databases. These databases list the estimated number of people (regardless of age) in each cell with size approximately 1x1 km in a global grid. Shapefiles defining the outline of national and subnational geographical boundaries were downloaded from The Humanitarian Data Exchange.⁸ Metadata of WHO STEPS surveys (e.g., eligible age ranges and included geographical areas) were downloaded from the WHO microdata repository website.²

Spatial analyses

Population sizes for whole countries and survey areas (for subnationally representative surveys) were extracted from the geospatial datasets by overlaying the shapefiles defining the relevant geographical areas on the population grid.

For each of the three gridded data sources (LandScan, WorldPop and GlobPOP), we calculated the total population of each country where at least one WHO STEPS survey had been conducted, for each of the years 2000-2020. Due to the large number of population estimates required, these calculations were based on raster methods instead of vector methods.⁹ For each of the surveys that were designed to be representative of only a subnational area, we also calculated the population of the survey area for each of the years 2000-2020.

Based on the evaluation of these population estimates (see below), it was decided to base our final calculations of source population sizes on the WorldPop dataset. To maximize the precision of our estimates, the final calculations were vector-based.⁹ These calculations were only conducted for specific countries and years

for which a subnational WHO STEPS survey had been conducted. While we considered basing the calculations on a version of the WorldPop dataset that had higher resolution (100×100 m),¹⁰ this plan had to be dropped because the higher resolution meant that calculations in vector format took unreasonably long.

For nationally representative surveys, $d_i = e_i$, meaning that $\frac{d_i}{e_i} = 1$, and Equation 2 can be reduced to Equation 3. For such surveys it would be a waste of computing resources to extract vector-based population estimates from WorldPop, so this was not done, and final estimates of source population sizes for such surveys were calculated using Equation 3.

Equation 3

$$a_{tot} = \sum_i b_i \times c_i \times f_i$$

Evaluation

For each of the countries where a WHO STEPS survey had been conducted, we created a list of total population estimates from the UN and from each of the gridded datasets (LandScan, WorldPop and GlobPOP) for each of the years 2000-2020. We assessed random fluctuations in the grid-based population estimates over time for each country by calculating the coefficient of determination (R^2) with calendar year as the explanatory variable and allowing for non-linearity by including calendar year as a second-degree polynomial. We assessed the similarity between the grid-based and UN population estimates by calculating their ratio for each country for each year. We assessed random fluctuations in the grid-based population estimates relative to the UN estimate by calculating the coefficient of determination (R^2) as described for calendar year. For each country, we created plots showing population sizes by year (in absolute numbers, and relative to the UN estimate for the same year).

For the surveys that were designed to be representative of only a smaller geographical area, we assessed random fluctuations in the relative size of the population in the survey area (relative to the population of the whole country) over time by plotting the relative population size against calendar year from 2000 to 2020. We summarized the plots numerically by calculating the coefficient of determination (R^2) with calendar year as the explanatory variable and allowing for non-linearity by including calendar year as a second-degree polynomial.

Software tools

Spatial analyses were performed in ArcGIS Pro 3.6.0 (Environmental Systems Research Institute, Redlands, California, US) and Python 3.6 (Python Software Foundation). Data management and all other analyses were done using Stata 15 (StataCorp, College Station, Texas, US).

Data and code availability

The analyses presented in this report are all based on publicly available anonymous data. For licensing reasons, the source data is not included with the report, but can be freely downloaded online, using the links provided. All source code for the analyses is included in Supplement A.

Results and discussion

The WHO microdata repository website listed 146 STEPS surveys conducted in 97 countries. Of these, 32 (22%) were designed to be subnationally representative. E.g., the [COD_2005_STEPS_v01](#) (Congo Democratic Republic 2005) survey was only representative of the Ville-Province of Kinshasa.

Results from calculations of the temporal stability of the grid-based population estimates and their degree of agreement with UN population estimates are displayed in Table S1 in Supplement B. Results on temporal stability of the relative population sizes in subnational survey areas are displayed in Table S2 in Supplement B. Results from both groups of analyses are summarized in Table 1.

It is clear from Table 1 that total population estimates showed fewer random fluctuations over time and relative to the UN estimates (expressed by higher R^2) for the WorldPop dataset, compared to the GlobPOP and LandScan datasets. It is also clear that the grid-based population estimates were more similar to UN estimates for WorldPop than for GlobPOP and LandScan (expressed by the ratios of the grid-based population sizes to the UN-based ones). Furthermore, Table 1 shows that the relative size of the survey area population (i.e., relative to the whole country) showed fewer random fluctuations for WorldPop than for GlobPOP and LandScan (expressed by higher R^2). Hence, it was decided to base our remaining analyses on the WorldPop datasets.

Table 2 lists the STEPS surveys that were designed to be subnationally representative, along with the ratio between the estimated survey area population and the whole country population $\left(\frac{d_i}{e_i}\right)$, based on data from WorldPop. Results are presented for both raster- and vector-based calculations. An expanded version of the table that includes not only the ratio, but also the absolute values of d_i and e_i , is available as Table S3 in Supplement B. The ratio between the survey area population and the population of the whole country $\left(\frac{d_i}{e_i}\right)$ is very similar, no matter which method of calculation was used. But theoretically, doing vector-based calculations is more accurate,⁹ so final calculations of source population sizes were based on this procedure.

Table 1: Summary of analyses comparing different geospatial population datasets

Metric	Gridded population dataset	N	Median	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Lower limit of IQR	Upper limit of IQR
Mean population of whole country relative to UN estimate	WorldPop	97	0.954	0.925	0.231	1.346	0.889	0.985
	GlobPOP	97	0.984	0.940	0.000	1.641	0.952	1.000
	LandScan	97	0.947	0.934	0.229	1.869	0.899	1.004
R ² for UN (total population)	WorldPop	97	0.998	0.917	0.056	1.000	0.979	1.000
	GlobPOP	95	0.995	0.924	0.057	1.000	0.971	1.000
	LandScan	97	0.931	0.801	0.028	0.998	0.710	0.978
R ² for calendar year (total population)	WorldPop	97	1.000	0.975	0.057	1.000	1.000	1.000
	GlobPOP	95	0.992	0.926	0.286	1.000	0.966	0.999
	LandScan	97	0.930	0.806	0.019	0.998	0.720	0.982
R ² for calendar year (survey area population relative to whole country population)	WorldPop	31	0.999	0.981	0.641	1.000	0.998	1.000
	GlobPOP	30	0.766	0.646	0.075	0.964	0.329	0.924
	LandScan	31	0.749	0.608	0.014	0.890	0.396	0.837

For most country-based summaries, N = 97. But when summarizing R² for UN and for calendar year, N = 95 for GlobPOP. This is because the extracted population size of both Tokelau and Niue was 0 (zero) for all years 2000-2020, when analyses were based on the GlobPOP dataset. Hence, the variation in estimated population size for these countries was 0, the R² was undefined and Tokelau and Niue were left out of the summary.

For summaries of subnational survey areas, N = 31 for WorldPop and LandScan, while N = 30 for GlobPOP. This is because 32 WHO STEPS surveys were subnationally representative. Out of these, the relative size of the survey areas population was constant across years 2000-2020 for the survey PSE_2010_STEPS_v01 (State of Palestine 2010), no matter the grid dataset used. The relative population size was constant for GlobPOP only for the survey MDV_2011_STEPS_v01 (Maldives 2011). When the relative size is constant, its variation is 0 (zero), the R² is undefined, and the survey is left out of the summary.

Table 2: Comparison of survey area weights based on raster and vector calculations on WorldPop data

Survey ID	Country			Year	Survey population as fraction of population for whole country $\left(\frac{d_i}{e_i}\right)$	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code		Raster	Vector
BEN_2007_STEPS_v01	Benin	BEN	BEN	2007	0.090	0.090
BTN_2007_STEPS_v01	Bhutan	BTN	BTN	2007	0.143	0.143
CAF_2010_STEPS_v01	Central African Republic	CAF	CAF	2010	0.147	0.146
CAF_2017_STEPS_v01	Central African Republic	CAF	CAF	2017	0.251	0.250
CIV_2005_STEPS_v01	Côte d'Ivoire	CIV	CIV	2005	0.234	0.234
COD_2005_STEPS_v01	Democratic Republic of the Congo	COD	COD	2005	0.099	0.099
COG_2004_STEPS_v01	Congo	COG	COG	2004	0.255	0.256
DZA_2003_STEPS_v01	Algeria	DZA	DZA	2003	0.066	0.066
ETH_2006_STEPS_v01	Ethiopia	ETH	ETH	2006	0.037	0.037
FSM_2002_STEPS-PNI_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2002	0.406	0.410
FSM_2006_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2006	0.412	0.405
FSM_2008_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2008	0.425	0.429
FSM_2009_STEPS-KSA_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2009	0.064	0.066
FSM_2009_STEPS-YAP_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2009	0.103	0.104
FSM_2016_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Fed. States of)	FSM	FSM	2016	0.389	0.383
GHA_2006_STEPS_v01	Ghana	GHA	GHA	2006	0.156	0.156
GIN_2009_STEPS_v01	Guinea	GIN	GIN	2009	0.369	0.369
LAO_2008_STEPS_v01	Lao People's Democratic Republic	LAO	LAO	2008	0.125	0.125
MDG_2005_STEPS_v01	Madagascar	MDG	MDG	2005	0.435	0.435
MDV_2011_STEPS_v01	Maldives	MDV	MDV	2011	0.351	0.239
MLI_2007_STEPS_v01	Mali	MLI	MLI	2007	0.128	0.126
MLI_2013_STEPS_v01	Mali	MLI	MLI	2013	0.166	0.164
MRT_2006_STEPS_v01	Mauritania	MRT	MRT	2006	0.248	0.248
PAK_2013_STEPS_v01	Pakistan	PAK	PAK	2013	0.770	0.770
PAK_2013_STEPS_v01	Pakistan	PAK	PAK	2014	0.771	0.771
PSE_2010_STEPS_v01	State of Palestine	PSE	PSE	2010	1.000	1.000
PSE_2010_STEPS_v01	State of Palestine	PSE	PSE	2011	1.000	1.000
SDN_2016_STEPS_v01	Sudan	SDN	SDN	2016	0.171	0.171
SLB_2006_STEPS_v01	Solomon Islands	SLB	SLB	2005	0.553	0.549
SLB_2006_STEPS_v01	Solomon Islands	SLB	SLB	2006	0.548	0.544
TCD_2008_STEPS_v01	Chad	TCD	TCD	2008	0.082	0.082
TZA_2011_STEPS_v01	United Republic of Tanzania	TZA	TZA	2011	0.028	0.028
TZA_2012_STEPS_v01	United Republic of Tanzania	TZA	TZA	2012	0.972	0.972
VUT_2005_STEPS_v01	Vanuatu	VUT	VUT	2005	0.285	0.283
ZMB_2008_STEPS_v01	Zambia	ZMB	ZMB	2008	0.161	0.161

Final estimates of source population sizes are provided in Table 3. In the survey [SDN_2016_STEPS_v01](#) (Sudan 2016), urine was only collected from participants in Khartoum State, but the survey was otherwise nationally representative. Therefore, source population estimates are provided separately for urine analyses and for other data (the two population estimates are the same for all countries except [SDN_2016_STEPS_v01](#)).

For a few surveys, we deemed it unlikely that we could calculate a valid estimate of the size of the source population, in most cases because the surveys used non-standard eligibility criteria. Hence, for the following surveys no source population size estimate is provided:

- [BRN_2015_STEPS_v01](#) (Brunei Darussalam 2015): Survey excluded anyone "diagnosed with terminal or incapacitating illnesses".
- [BWA_2007_STEPS_v01](#) (Botswana 2007): Only included persons from locations with population \geq 5,000.
- [CMR_2003_STEPS_v01](#) (Cameroon 2003): The survey area was described as "Four urban sentinel sites from each of four ecological zones of the country."
- [GAB_2009_STEPS_v01](#) (Gabon 2009): Designed to be subnationally representative, but we were unable to locate shapefiles corresponding to the relevant geographical area (Libreville and Owendo).
- [KWT_2006_STEPS_v01](#) (Kuwait 2006): Only included Kuwaiti nationals.
- [URY_2013_STEPS_v01](#) (Uruguay 2013): Only included persons from locations with population \geq 10,000.

Some researchers might be interested in analyzing only WHO STEPS data for specific groups defined by age and sex. In Table S4 in Supplement B we have included a database of source population sizes for each survey, stratified by sex and 1-year age groups. Results in Table S4 were prepared in the same way as Table 3, apart from the stratification.

Conclusion

Population estimates from grid-based calculations using WorldPop datasets were more temporally stable and showed a higher degree of agreement with UN population estimates, compared to estimates based on GlobPOP and LandScan datasets. We have provided a table of source population size estimates for all the WHO STEPS surveys where enough information was available to allow such estimation.

Table 3: Final source population size estimates for WHO STEPS surveys

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
ABW_2023_STEPS_v01	Aruba	ABW	ABW	National		18	69	74,489	74,489
AFG_2018_STEPS_v01	Afghanistan	AFG	AFG	National		18	69	17,045,936	17,045,936
ARM_2016_STEPS_v01	Armenia	ARM	ARM	National		18	69	2,009,139	2,009,139
ASM_2004_STEPS_v01	American Samoa	ASM	ASM	National		25	64	23,894	23,894
AZE_2017_STEPS_v01	Azerbaijan	AZE	AZE	National		18	69	6,857,830	6,857,830
BEN_2007_STEPS_v01	Benin	BEN	BEN	Subnational	Cotonou	25	64	265,105	265,105
BEN_2008_STEPS_v01	Benin	BEN	BEN	National		25	64	3,037,320	3,037,320
BEN_2015_STEPS_v01	Benin	BEN	BEN	National		18	69	5,488,629	5,488,629
BFA_2021_STEPS_v01	Burkina Faso	BFA	BFA	National		18	69	10,599,173	10,599,173
BGD_2009_STEPS_v01	Bangladesh	BGD	BGD	National		25	-	69,678,168	69,678,168
BGD_2018_STEPS_v01	Bangladesh	BGD	BGD	National		18	69	99,032,632	99,032,632
BHS_2011_STEPS_v01	Bahamas	BHS	BHS	National		25	64	189,558	189,558
BHS_2019_STEPS_v01	Bahamas	BHS	BHS	National		18	69	270,141	270,141
BLR_2016_STEPS_v01	Belarus	BLR	BLR	National		18	69	6,738,516	6,738,516
BOL_2019_STEPS_v01	Bolivia (Plurinational State of)	BOL	BOL	National		18	69	6,908,607	6,908,607
BRB_2007_STEPS_v01	Barbados	BRB	BRB	National		25	-	176,981	176,981
BRN_2015_STEPS_v01	Brunei Darussalam	BRN	BRN	National		18	69	-	-
BTN_2007_STEPS_v01	Bhutan	BTN	BTN	Subnational	Thimphu	25	74	42,598	42,598
BTN_2014_STEPS_v01	Bhutan	BTN	BTN	National		18	69	462,014	462,014
BTN_2019_STEPS_v01	Bhutan	BTN	BTN	National		15	69	551,284	551,284
BVI_2009_STEPS_v01	British Virgin Islands	BVI	VGB	National		25	64	16,012	16,012
BWA_2007_STEPS_v01	Botswana	BWA	BWA	National		25	64	-	-
BWA_2014_STEPS_v01	Botswana	BWA	BWA	National		15	69	1,378,213	1,378,213
CAF_2010_STEPS_v01	Central African Republic	CAF	CAF	Subnational	Bangui	25	64	203,614	203,614
CAF_2017_STEPS_v01	Central African Republic	CAF	CAF	Subnational	Bangui and Ombella M'Poko	15	64	585,165	585,165

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
CIV_2005_STEPS_v01	Côte d'Ivoire	CIV	CIV	Subnational	Health regions of Lagunes 1 and 2 (Abidjan and surrounds)	15	64	2,412,244	2,412,244
CMR_2003_STEPS_v01	Cameroon	CMR	CMR	National		15	-	-	-
COD_2005_STEPS_v01	Democratic Republic of the Congo	COD	COD	Subnational	Ville-Province of Kinshasa	15	-	3,150,585	3,150,585
COG_2004_STEPS_v01	Congo	COG	COG	Subnational	Brazzaville	25	64	323,684	323,684
COK_2003_STEPS_v01	Cook Islands	COK	COK	National		25	64	6,715	6,715
COK_2013_STEPS_v01	Cook Islands	COK	COK	National		18	64	10,573	10,573
COM_2011_STEPS_v01	Comoros	COM	COM	National		25	64	224,897	224,897
CPV_2007_STEPS_v01	Cabo Verde	CPV	CPV	National		25	64	183,357	183,357
CPV_2020_STEPS_v01	Cabo Verde	CPV	CPV	National		18	69	321,208	321,208
CYM_2012_STEPS_v01	Cayman Islands	CYM	CYM	National		25	64	36,940	36,940
DZA_2003_STEPS_v01	Algeria	DZA	DZA	Subnational	Setif and Mostaganem	25	64	887,828	887,828
DZA_2016_STEPS_v01	Algeria	DZA	DZA	National		18	69	26,028,940	26,028,940
ECU_2018_STEPS_v01	Ecuador	ECU	ECU	National		18	69	10,662,404	10,662,404
ERI_2004_STEPS_v01	Eritrea	ERI	ERI	National		15	64	1,394,310	1,394,310
ERI_2010_STEPS_v01	Eritrea	ERI	ERI	National		25	74	1,073,066	1,073,066
ETH_2006_STEPS_v01	Ethiopia	ETH	ETH	Subnational	Addis Ababa	25	64	938,948	938,948
ETH_2015_STEPS_v01	Ethiopia	ETH	ETH	National		15	69	57,608,192	57,608,192
FJI_2002_STEPS_v01	Fiji	FJI	FJI	National		15	64	540,421	540,421
FJI_2011_STEPS_v01	Fiji	FJI	FJI	National		25	64	423,637	423,637
FSM_2002_STEPS-PNI_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Pohnpei	25	64	16,531	16,531
FSM_2006_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Chuuk	15	64	26,501	26,501
FSM_2008_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Pohnpei	25	64	18,492	18,492
FSM_2009_STEPS-KSA_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Kosrae	25	64	2,852	2,852
FSM_2009_STEPS-YAP_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Yap	15	64	6,789	6,789
FSM_2016_STEPS_v01	Micronesia (Federated States of)	FSM	FSM	Subnational	Chuuk	18	69	23,908	23,908

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
GAB_2009_STEPS_v01	Gabon	GAB	GAB	Subnational	Libreville and Owendo	15	64	-	-
GEO_2010_STEPS_v01	Georgia	GEO	GEO	National		18	64	2,484,305	2,484,305
GEO_2016_STEPS_v01	Georgia	GEO	GEO	National		18	69	2,544,064	2,544,064
GHA_2006_STEPS_v01	Ghana	GHA	GHA	Subnational	Greater Accra Region	25	64	1,283,579	1,283,579
GIN_2009_STEPS_v01	Guinea	GIN	GIN	Subnational	Basse Guinee and Conakry	15	64	1,930,634	1,930,634
GMB_2010_STEPS_v01	Gambia	GMB	GMB	National		25	64	618,045	618,045
GRD_2010_STEPS_v01	Grenada	GRD	GRD	National		25	64	52,752	52,752
GUY_2016_STEPS_v01	Guyana	GUY	GUY	National		18	69	461,144	461,144
IRQ_2015_STEPS_v01	Iraq	IRQ	IRQ	National		18	-	19,944,450	19,944,450
JOR_2019_STEPS_v01	Jordan	JOR	JOR	National		18	69	6,269,022	6,269,022
KEN_2015_STEPS_v01	Kenya	KEN	KEN	National		18	69	23,476,768	23,476,768
KGZ_2013_STEPS_v01	Kyrgyzstan	KGZ	KGZ	National		25	64	2,589,800	2,589,800
KHM_2010_STEPS_v01	Cambodia	KHM	KHM	National		25	64	5,889,019	5,889,019
KIR_2004_STEPS_v01	Kiribati	KIR	KIR	National		15	64	57,280	57,280
KIR_2015_STEPS_v01	Kiribati	KIR	KIR	National		18	69	66,564	66,564
KWT_2006_STEPS_v01	Kuwait	KWT	KWT	National		20	64	-	-
KWT_2014_STEPS_v01	Kuwait	KWT	KWT	National		18	69	2,687,307	2,687,307
LAO_2013_STEPS_v01	Lao People's Democratic Republic	LAO	LAO	National		18	64	3,637,154	3,637,154
LBN_2017_STEPS_v01	Lebanon	LBN	LBN	National	National coverage of Lebanese and Syrian populations (two separate samples)	18	69	3,886,314	3,886,314
LBR_2011_STEPS_v01	Liberia	LBR	LBR	National		25	64	1,480,942	1,480,942
LBR_2022_STEPS_v01	Liberia	LBR	LBR	National		18	69	2,722,355	2,722,355
LBY_2009_STEPS_v01	Libya	LBY	LBY	National		25	64	2,925,840	2,925,840
LCA_2019_STEPS_v01	Saint Lucia	LCA	LCA	National		18	69	127,017	127,017
LKA_2006_STEPS_v01	Sri Lanka	LKA	LKA	National		15	64	13,741,706	13,741,706
LKA_2014_STEPS_v01	Sri Lanka	LKA	LKA	National		18	69	14,128,676	14,128,676
LKA_2021_STEPS_v01	Sri Lanka	LKA	LKA	National		18	69	14,826,481	14,826,481
LSO_2012_STEPS_v01	Lesotho	LSO	LSO	National		25	64	746,354	746,354

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
LAO_2008_STEPS_v01	Lao People's Democratic Republic	LAO	LAO	Subnational	Vientiane Capital City	25	64	279,048	279,048
MAR_2017_STEPS_v01	Morocco	MAR	MAR	National		18	-	23,838,838	23,838,838
MDA_2013_STEPS_v01	Republic of Moldova	MDA	MDA	National		18	69	2,422,994	2,422,994
MDA_2021_STEPS_v01	Republic of Moldova	MDA	MDA	National		18	69	2,045,358	2,045,358
MDG_2005_STEPS_v01	Madagascar	MDG	MDG	Subnational	Antananarivo and Toliara	25	64	2,750,095	2,750,095
MDV_2011_STEPS_v01	Maldives	MDV	MDV	Subnational	Male	15	64	63,162	63,162
MHL_2002_STEPS_v01	Marshall Islands	MHL	MHL	National		15	64	29,398	29,398
MHL_2017_STEPS_v01	Marshall Islands	MHL	MHL	National		18	-	26,462	26,462
MLI_2007_STEPS_v01	Mali	MLI	MLI	Subnational	District of Bamako, Commune of Kati central and Commune of Ouéléssebougou	15	64	916,230	916,230
MLI_2013_STEPS_v01	Mali	MLI	MLI	Subnational	Kati, Ouéléssebougou, Koulikoro, Ségou and Bamako District	15	65	1,421,323	1,421,323
MNG_2005_STEPS_v01	Mongolia	MNG	MNG	National		15	64	1,705,547	1,705,547
MNG_2009_STEPS_v01	Mongolia	MNG	MNG	National		15	64	1,820,452	1,820,452
MNG_2013_STEPS_v01	Mongolia	MNG	MNG	National		15	64	1,932,351	1,932,351
MNG_2019_STEPS_v01	Mongolia	MNG	MNG	National		15	69	2,104,678	2,104,678
MOZ_2005_STEPS_v01	Mozambique	MOZ	MOZ	National		25	64	6,463,386	6,463,386
MRT_2006_STEPS_v01	Mauritania	MRT	MRT	Subnational	Nouakchott	15	64	393,524	393,524
MWI_2009_STEPS_v01_M	Malawi	MWI	MWI	National		25	64	4,275,024	4,275,024
MWI_2017_STEPS_v01	Malawi	MWI	MWI	National		18	69	8,405,577	8,405,577
NAM_2005_STEPS_v01	Namibia	NAM	NAM	National		25	64	714,523	714,523
NER_2007_STEPS_v01	Niger	NER	NER	National		15	64	7,217,183	7,217,183
NIU_2011_STEPS_v01	Niue	NIU	NIU	National		15	-	1,297	1,297
NPL_2012_STEPS_v01	Nepal	NPL	NPL	National		15	69	17,255,016	17,255,016
NPL_2019_STEPS_v01	Nepal	NPL	NPL	National		15	69	18,600,154	18,600,154
NRU_2004_STEPS_v01	Nauru	NRU	NRU	National		15	64	6,177	6,177
NRU_2015_STEPS_v01	Nauru	NRU	NRU	National		18	69	6,148	6,148
PAK_2013_STEPS_v01	Pakistan	PAK	PAK	Subnational	Punjab and Sindh provinces of Pakistan	18	69	85,886,656	85,886,656

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
PLW_2011_STEPS_v01	Palau	PLW	PLW	National		25	64	10,372	10,372
PLW_2016_STEPS_v01	Palau	PLW	PLW	National		18	-	13,539	13,539
PSE_2010_STEPS_v01	Occupied Palestinian Territory	PSE	PSE	Subnational	West Bank and Gaza Strip	15	64	2,233,168	2,233,168
PYF_2010_STEPS_v01	French Polynesia	PYF	PYF	National		18	64	169,270	169,270
QAT_2012_STEPS_v01	Qatar	QAT	QAT	National		18	64	1,572,426	1,572,426
RWA_2012_STEPS_v01	Rwanda	RWA	RWA	National		15	64	6,093,080	6,093,080
SDN_2016_STEPS_v01	Sudan	SDN	SDN	National	National except for urine collection (Khartoum State only)	18	69	19,970,754	3,418,288
SLB_2006_STEPS_v01	Solomon Islands	SLB	SLB	Subnational	Honiara, Western Province and Malaita	15	64	147,516	147,516
SLB_2015_STEPS_v01	Solomon Islands	SLB	SLB	National		18	69	329,071	329,071
SLE_2009_STEPS_v01	Sierra Leone	SLE	SLE	National		25	64	2,049,358	2,049,358
STP_2009_STEPS_v01	Sao Tome and Principe	STP	STP	National		25	64	58,411	58,411
STP_2019_STEPS_v01	Sao Tome and Principe	STP	STP	National		18	69	107,243	107,243
SWZ_2007_STEPS_v01	Eswatini	SWZ	SWZ	National		25	64	367,972	367,972
SWZ_2014_STEPS_v01	Eswatini	SWZ	SWZ	National		15	69	692,423	692,423
SYC_2004_STEPS_v01	Seychelles	SYC	SYC	National		25	64	43,663	43,663
TCD_2008_STEPS_v01	Chad	TCD	TCD	Subnational	N'Djamena	25	64	285,735	285,735
TGO_2010_STEPS_v01	Togo	TGO	TGO	National		15	64	3,798,070	3,798,070
TJK_2016_STEPS_v01	Tajikistan	TJK	TJK	National		18	69	4,985,277	4,985,277
TKL_2005_STEPS_v01	Tokelau	TKL	TKL	National		15	64	918	918
TKL_2014_STEPS_v01	Tokelau	TKL	TKL	National		18	69	1,018	1,018
TKM_2018_STEPS_v01	Turkmenistan	TKM	TKM	National		18	69	4,178,848	4,178,848
TLS_2014_STEPS_v01	Timor-Leste	TLS	TLS	National		18	69	595,110	595,110
TON_2004_STEPS_v01	Tonga	TON	TON	National		15	64	59,037	59,037
TON_2011_STEPS_v01	Tonga	TON	TON	National		25	64	40,923	40,923
TON_2017_STEPS_v01	Tonga	TON	TON	National		18	69	55,785	55,785
TTO_2024_STEPS_v01	Trinidad and Tobago	TTO	TTO	National		18	69	1,065,293	1,065,293
TUV_2015_STEPS_v01	Tuvalu	TUV	TUV	National		18	69	6,481	6,481
TZA_2011_STEPS_v01	United Republic of Tanzania	TZA	TZA	Subnational	Zanzibar	25	64	411,797	411,797

Survey ID	Country			Survey national or subnational	Survey area (if subnational)	Age range		Estimated size of source population	
	Name	UN abbreviation	ISO3 code			Lower limit	Upper limit	All analyses except urine analyses	Urine analyses
TZA_2012_STEPS_v01	United Republic of Tanzania	TZA	TZA	Subnational	Tanzania excluding Zanzibar	25	64	14,883,082	14,883,082
UGA_2014_STEPS_v01	Uganda	UGA	UGA	National		18	69	15,634,199	15,634,199
UKR_2019_STEPS_v01	Ukraine	UKR	UKR	National		18	69	31,919,826	31,919,826
URY_2006_STEPS_v01	Uruguay	URY	URY	National		25	64	1,574,550	1,574,550
URY_2013_STEPS_v01	Uruguay	URY	URY	National		15	64	-	-
VNM_2009_STEPS_v01	Viet Nam	VNM	VNM	National		25	64	42,569,244	42,569,244
VNM_2015_STEPS_v01	Viet Nam	VNM	VNM	National		18	69	62,605,704	62,605,704
VNM_2021_STEPS_v01	Viet Nam	VNM	VNM	National		18	69	66,156,348	66,156,348
VUT_2005_STEPS_v01	Vanuatu	VUT	VUT	Subnational	Efate island only	15	60	33,257	33,257
VUT_2011_STEPS_v01	Vanuatu	VUT	VUT	National		25	64	92,729	92,729
WLF_2019_STEPS_v01	Wallis and Futuna	WLF	WLF	National		18	69	7,232	7,232
WSM_2002_STEPS_v01	Samoa	WSM	WSM	National		25	64	67,678	67,678
WSM_2013_STEPS_v01	Samoa	WSM	WSM	National		18	64	100,391	100,391
ZMB_2008_STEPS_v01	Zambia	ZMB	ZMB	Subnational	Lusaka	25	-	682,332	682,332
ZMB_2017_STEPS_v01	Zambia	ZMB	ZMB	National		18	69	8,332,660	8,332,660

Supplements

This report is published along with the following supplements:

Supplement	Filename	Description
A	Supplement_A.zip	ZIP file containing analysis code to reproduce results
B	Supplement_B.zip	Zip file containing CSV and HTML tables of results

Overview of tables

Table number	Title	Included in report?	Included in Supplement B?
1	Summary of analyses comparing different geospatial population datasets	✓	✓
2	Comparison of survey area weights based on raster and vector calculations on WorldPop data	✓	✓
3	Final source population size estimates for WHO STEPS surveys	✓	✓
S1	Results from analyses comparing geospatial datasets for each included country	-	✓
S2	Results from analyses comparing geospatial datasets for sub-national surveys	-	✓
S3	Comparison of survey area weights based on raster and vector calculations on WorldPop data (expanded)	-	✓
S4	Source population size estimates for each survey, stratified by sex and 1-year age groups	-	✓

Legal disclaimer

The World Health Organization has not been involved in the planning, conduct, interpretation or reporting of the analyses described in this document.

CRedit author statement

MRHH: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition.

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Ethics

This report describes results from analyses of publicly available data that are not personally identifiable. Under Danish legislation, such analyses do not need to undergo ethical review,¹¹ and the project was therefore not reviewed by an ethics committee.

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Conflicts of interest

The author has no financial or non-financial conflicts of interest to disclose.

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